

УНИВЕРЗИТЕТ У НОВОМ САДУ, МЕДИЦИНСКИ ФАКУЛТЕТ
UNIVERSITY OF NOVI SAD, FACULTY OF MEDICINE

СЕКЦИЈА ЗА ХИГИЈЕНУ СРПСКОГ ЛЕКАРСКОГ ДРУШТВА
SERBIAN MEDICAL SOCIETY, HYGIENE SECTION

**ПОД ПОКРОВИТЕЉСТВОМ МИНИСТАРСТВА ЗДРАВЉА И МИНИСТАРСТВА ПРОСВЕТЕ,
НАУКЕ И ТЕХНОЛОШКОГ РАЗВОЈА РЕПУБЛИКЕ СРБИЈЕ**

**UNDER THE PATRONAGE OF THE MINISTRY OF HEALTH AND THE MINISTRY OF EDUCATION,
SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGICAL DEVELOPMENT OF THE REPUBLIC OF SERBIA**

МЕЂУНАРОДНИ КОНГРЕС
INTERNATIONAL CONGRESS

ДРУГИ МЕЂУНАРОДНИ КОНГРЕС ХИГИЈЕНЕ И ПРЕВЕНТИВНЕ МЕДИЦИНЕ
“ИЗАЗОВИ И ЈАВНОЗДРАВСТВЕНЕ ИНТЕРВЕНЦИЈЕ”

SECOND INTERNATIONAL CONGRESS ON HYGIENE AND PREVENTIVE MEDICINE
“CHALLENGES AND PUBLIC HEALTH INTERVENTIONS”

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ABSTRACT BOOK

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PROGRAMME „COMPETENCE STRENGTHENING IN WORKING WITH YOUTH”

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Programme „Competence Strengthening in Working with Youth” presents one of the preventive programmes of Department of Mental Health and Addiction Prevention at Andrija Stampar Teaching Institute of Public Health. The goal of the programme is to decrease risky behaviour, i.e. the tendency to consume psychoactive substances as well as development of other forms of addictive and risky behaviours among youth. The competences of teachers and professional associates, considering their daily work routine, are strengthened through classes and workshops related to the issue of risky behaviour in youth.

Since September 2016. by January 2019. there were 45 high schools and 20 elementary schools included in the Programme, i.e. 1696 teachers and professional as-

sociates.

The Programme has been actively carried out for four years, has been well adopted and the final evaluation suggests its benefits concerning both personal and professional growth. Participants evaluated the implementation of the Programme with 1 to 5 grading scale resulting in total grade of 4,4 for all segments.

Implementation of this Programme is an example of good practice and collaboration of health and educational sectors with respect to prevention of harmful patterns of youth behaviour. Assessment of implementation as well as positive comments indicate the need for further application of the Programme.

KEY WORDS: youth, risky behaviour, school, competences

THE INCIDENCE OF BURNOUT AMONG CRITICAL CARE NURSES: A SHORT CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY

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INTRODUCTION: Contemporary nursing is considered one of the most stressful jobs requiring a simultaneous mental, physical and emotional engagement. As expected, the exposure of nurses to occupational stressors is most significant in critical care units. Nowadays, critical care units have been recognized as one of the most stressful working environment in global human professional activity, particularly for nurses, who are in a close contact with hospitalized patients throughout all of their working hours.

AIM: To assess the incidence of professional burnout among critical care nurses, by using the inventory based on Freudenberger Burnout Scale.

METHODS: This research was designed as a mini cross-sectional psychometric study in September 2017. The study included 71 nurses employed in critical care units of surgery, urology, internal medicine, pediatrics,

gynecology, obstetrics, and otorhinolaryngology departments in one of five university hospital centers in Belgrade, Serbia.

RESULTS: The statistical analysis of the data obtained in this study showed alarming results - burnout syndrome affected approximately one-third of the observed subjects, in form of manifested or severe job burnout. In the same time, another one-third of subjects were classified in the category of burnout candidates.

CONCLUSION: Burnout involvement in observed sample exceeds the mean frequency of job burnout among critical care nurses in other European countries that have been reported in the available literature sources.

KEY WORDS: critical care nurse, job burnout, risk factors